

Your C-suite Guide

**Renewing biodiversity through
a people-in-nature approach**

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Executive Summary

Towards Nature-Positive Business

‘Nature’ is the natural world – land, oceans, rivers, air, soils and all living things – and ‘biodiversity’ is the variety of that life and ecosystems that nature relies on to function, just like your business.¹ ‘Nature positive’ means halting and reversing biodiversity and nature loss so that business activities contribute to recovery rather than decline.

Over 55% of global GDP (~\$58 trillion) is moderately or highly dependent on nature, and in the UK unchecked nature loss could shave around 5% off GDP by 2030.² Companies are already feeling this in concrete ways: large fines for pollution, nature-related disruptions to supply chains, and invasive species costing the UK economy billions annually³, and long-term asset owners expanding their toolkits to address the systemic climate-nature risks that threaten long-term returns.⁴ At the same time, firms that act are finding real upside. One UK water company’s deployment of nature-based solutions avoided the need to invest capital in new treatment works, saving around £100 million while improving water quality and biodiversity.⁵

Global policy and finance signals are tightening even as the geopolitical backdrop is becoming more contested. In several major markets, nature and climate initiatives have faced increasing political pushback, sometimes leading to delays, dilution, or re-framing of environmental measures, reinforcing why companies should anchor nature action in long-term risk management and resilience, not short-term political cycles.⁶

The *Kunming–Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework*, the UK’s Biodiversity Net Gain rules, voluntary disclosure frameworks

such as the Taskforce on Nature-related Financial Disclosures (TNFD), and emerging Science-Based Targets for Nature (SBTN) all point in the same direction: by 2030, businesses will be expected to understand, manage and disclose their nature-related dependencies, impacts, risks and opportunities. Yet:

- Globally only one in four companies currently treat biodiversity as a high priority, and
- UK data show that nature stewardship still lags behind other aspects of responsible business.⁷

This gap is both a warning and a first-mover opportunity.

Our research with senior leaders in the UK reveals why progress is slow:

- External policy and price signals for nature still trail those for climate, making it harder to build a near-term business case.
- Nature rarely appears as a strategic topic at board level unless the company or value chain has direct impact or is directly impacted.
- Ownership is fragmented across functions such as sustainability, operations and communications teams; and

- Financial allocation processes struggle to recognise longer-horizon resilience and avoided-risk benefits.
- Pockets of expertise often sit in overstretched teams, over-reliance on consultants slows internal capability-building, and the complexity of location-specific metrics creates ‘perfection paralysis’: companies wait for perfect data instead of acting on good enough, decision-useful evidence.
- Fear of being accused of greenwashing then leads some to stay quiet about modest, early-stage efforts, stifling learning, momentum and inspiration for others. Fear of being targeted by shareholder activists (and others) for public commitments to nature and climate also truncate efforts.⁸

Our work also highlighted how hard it is to find credible, decision-useful examples of UK companies genuinely integrating biodiversity and nature at scale into strategy and operations unless from sectors directly affecting nature and biodiversity such as infrastructure, utilities, construction and extractive industries. **Much current activity remains voluntary, project-based and thinly reported, which likely reflects the early stage of this agenda and the absence, so far, of strong mandates in sectors less-directly connected with nature and biodiversity.**

Over 55% of global GDP

~\$58 trillion

is moderately or highly dependent on nature

In the UK unchecked nature loss could shave around

5% off GDP

by 2030.²

In the more advanced examples in this guide, common threads are beginning to emerge. These companies:

- Treat forthcoming regulation, investor expectations and market trends as a planning assumption rather than a surprise.
- Draw on simple route maps such as ACT-D (Assess, Commit, Transform, Disclose) and LEAP (Locate, Evaluate, Assess, Prepare) to organise their efforts.
- Signal at board and C-suite level that biodiversity and nature are strategic, set an ambition and assign clear ownership.
- Start to weave nature into risk, procurement, product and site decisions rather than bolting it on; and
- Use employees, internal ‘translators’ and external partners (NGOs, academics, local authorities, regulators and coalitions) to build place-based expertise and credibility.

Where possible, this guide points to such documented examples – but their relative scarcity is itself a signal of how much work still lies ahead.

It is useful for leadership teams to understand where they are starting from. This guide therefore sets out six types of company that leaders can use to reflect on their current position and challenges. These are not intended as labels, but as a simple rule of thumb to prompt honest discussion about where different parts of the business are today and what credible next steps might look like. Some organisations may recognise themselves in Agenda Setters, shaping norms and piloting new frameworks; others in Trailblazers, embedding nature across financing, suppliers and operations. Many

will see features of Emerging Leaders, committed internally and sometimes ahead of regulation but constrained by context; Pressured Beginners, pushed into action by customers, regulators or investors and responding reactively; Backsliders, where commitments are being withdrawn; or Unengaged firms, where nature has yet to feature meaningfully on the agenda. Different parts of the same company may sit in different places on this spectrum, and making that variation visible – including any tension between ambitious statements and business-as-usual lobbying – is an important foundation for credible action.

This guide lays bare where business stands today on biodiversity and nature and makes the case that waiting for 2030 is no longer an option. It gives the C-suite a simple four-tier model – externalities, company response, operationalisation and evidence – to frame the problem, and then focuses hard on the next two years: clarify where your business depends on and affects nature, choose a handful of high-leverage hotspots, run targeted pilots with credible partners, and translate what works into policies, standards and KPIs that can be scaled across sites and suppliers.

Rather than prescribing a one-size-fits-all solution, it highlights how the same management logic already used in core business functions such as finance, operations and procurement can be applied here: a scorecard of process and performance indicators, linked to enterprise value and built into existing scorecards and dashboards. This guide is a first step and a springboard for collaboration between businesses, government agencies, investors, academia, business networks and NGOs to develop sector- and function-specific implementation guidance.

For leaders in the C-suite, the ask is straightforward:

- Put biodiversity and nature explicitly on the board and executive agenda.
- Have an honest discussion about where you are today across the six company types, recognising that different parts of the business may be in different places.
- Develop a two-year roadmap with clear hotspots, pilots, ownership and review points.
- Add a set of nature-related metrics⁹ to your core KPIs, and back your people and partners to experiment, learn and scale what works.
- Encourage first-hand experiential engagement with nature as a way to build cultural and interpersonal commitments.

Companies that do this will not only help halt and reverse nature loss; they will also future-proof their own success in an economy that is rapidly rewiring around nature-positive performance.

In brief:

- Business depends on nature for growth and resilience – over half of global GDP, and around 5% of UK GDP by 2030, is at risk if nature loss continues unchecked, hitting key sectors such as agriculture, manufacturing, housing, energy and tourism.
- Ignoring nature risks real costs (fines, supply shocks, liabilities), while nature-positive strategies can cut costs and unlock new value.
- Policy and investor signals are tightening fast, yet most companies still under-prioritise nature, creating both a growing risk and a first-mover opportunity

Why Biodiversity and Nature Matter for Business

'Nature' is the natural world – its land, oceans, rivers, air, soils and all living things, including people – and 'biodiversity' is the variety of that life and ecosystems that nature relies on to function. 'Nature positive' means halting and reversing the loss of biodiversity and nature. It's about ensuring that business activities contribute to recovery rather than decline to protect and restore the natural systems that underpin economic and social prosperity and wellbeing.¹⁰ This guide is a first step to orient leaders and a springboard for more detailed sector- and function-specific implementation guidance.

Your company depends on and affects biodiversity and nature. Over 55% of global GDP (~\$58 trillion) is moderately or highly dependent on nature.¹¹ In the UK, some estimates suggest unchecked nature loss could shave around 5% off GDP by 2030, undermining current growth initiatives.¹² Industries from agriculture to construction rely on ecosystem services like pollination, clean water, and climate stability.

Companies that ignore biodiversity- and nature-related risks could face supply chain disruptions, regulatory penalties, and reputational damage – as seen when a publicly listed water utility received a £90 million fine for illegal sewage discharges into protected coastal waters¹³. Invasive non-native species are now estimated to cost the UK economy around £4 billion a year, hitting the agriculture sector with increased costs estimated over £1 billion.¹⁴

Conversely, embracing a 'nature-positive' strategy¹⁵ can spur innovation, create jobs, ensure wellbeing and build resilience¹⁶ – Wessex Water's nature-based solutions approach, working with farmers to reduce agricultural runoff, avoided the need for new treatment works and saved around £100 million, while also improving water quality and biodiversity.¹⁷

Global agreements such as the 2022 *Kunming–Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework* (GBF) task governments with putting policies and mechanisms in place for businesses to assess, manage and

disclose their biodiversity and nature-related dependencies, impacts, risks and opportunities—signalling the direction of travel for corporate action by 2030.¹⁸ This global ambition is reflected nationally through the UK's National Biodiversity Strategy and Action Plan (NBSAP), which sets out how government intends to implement the GBF domestically. While the NBSAP itself is addressed to government delivery, it signals the policy direction—with related UK measures (e.g., England's mandatory Biodiversity Net Gain in planning and efforts to grow high-integrity nature markets) creating the expectations and incentives under which businesses will operate.¹⁹

Investors and regulators are raising expectations²⁰ – for example, voluntary disclosure frameworks e.g. the Taskforce on Nature-related Financial Disclosures (TNFD) and Science-Based Targets for Nature (SBTN)²¹ are gaining traction. In short, safeguarding biodiversity and nature is fast becoming a core element of business leadership, much like tackling climate change.

At the same time, progress is uneven across regions and sectors. In some markets, political and legal headwinds are prompting a more cautious stance on sustainability commitments and disclosure, and some companies are responding by lowering the profile of their nature and climate activity²²—even where internal work continues. Against this wider backdrop, the UK's direction of travel is clear, but the visibility of credible, decision-useful corporate practice can still lag behind policy ambition.

Our work has highlighted how hard it is to find credible, decision-useful examples of UK companies integrating biodiversity and nature at scale into strategy and operations outside sectors such as infrastructure, utilities, construction and extractive industries. Much current activity remains voluntary, project-based and thinly reported, reflecting both the early stage of this agenda and the absence, so far, of strong mandates in many less directly nature-exposed sectors.

Key Insight:

Business leaders increasingly recognise that biodiversity and nature risk is business risk.²³

2024 global survey found only 25% of companies currently treat biodiversity as a high priority.

Compared to two-thirds that prioritise climate action.

And 80% of sustainability professionals say their firms aren't doing enough about nature.

This gap is both a warning and an opportunity: those firms that act decisively now will lead their industries, while the unengaged risk falling behind as the nature-positive transition accelerates.

What's Holding Companies Back?

Six Key and Connected Barriers to Action

In brief:

- Six connected barriers slow action on nature and biodiversity: weak external signals, low salience, unclear ownership, operating-model gaps, data complexity and greenwashing anxiety.
- These show up as nature being off the strategic agenda, sitting in overstretched teams, and stalling in 'perfection paralysis' while others fear being called out for greenwashing.
- They are real but manageable: with clear leadership, better translation into core processes, and a pragmatic evidence journey, companies can move from intent to scalable action.

Through primary research with executives and senior leaders in the UK, we've identified recurring barriers that keep companies from fully engaging with biodiversity and nature. Understanding these is the first step to overcoming them:

1. External Signals and Economics

Companies operate within policy and market systems where biodiversity and nature signals lag those for climate. Regulation is evolving but inconsistent; ecosystem services are undervalued; and harmful subsidies persist (>\$2.6 trillion per year globally).²⁵ This weakens near-term incentives, making it harder to justify investments without a clear narrative on value creation and risk reduction.

So what?

Observe the direction of travel; participate in coalitions that shape standards and markets; pilot place-based partnerships that deliver tangible co-benefits and proof points.

2. Low Salience and Short-Termism

In many firms, nature and biodiversity simply aren't on the strategic radar. Senior leaders often view them as less immediate than quarterly performance or even climate commitments. This lowers internal priority and makes it harder for biodiversity and nature initiatives to secure high-level sponsorship and budget. Only 1 in 4 companies currently place high priority on biodiversity and nature, partly because the business case is diffuse across functions and not yet framed in decision-makers' terms.²⁶

So what?

Elevate salience by linking nature dependencies and impacts to core enterprise risks and opportunities (supply security, licence to operate, product differentiation, cost of capital, reputation). This is leadership work: set direction, expectations and accountability.

3. Governance, Ownership and Response

Nature goals can drift without clear high-level ownership. Ambitions are sometimes housed in specific corporate functions (e.g., communications, operations or sustainability teams) rather than governed as a strategic risk-and-opportunity domain. Incentives and resource allocation processes rarely recognise longer-horizon resilience and risk-avoidance benefits.

So what?

Assign executive-level accountability; integrate biodiversity and nature with enterprise risk processes that address related challenges like climate and circularity; update investment criteria so longer-dated benefits and avoided costs are visible in decisions.

Reality Check:

These barriers are real, but not insurmountable. They echo what research finds – e.g. *internal issues* like low awareness, short-term outlook, and difficulty measuring impacts, and *external issues* like weak regulatory alignment and lack of incentives. By addressing each through leadership response, operating-model design and a pragmatic evidence journey, companies can move from intent to scalable action on biodiversity and nature.

4. Operating-Model Gaps and Translation Failures

Even where pockets of expertise exist, they often sit in small, over-stretched teams. We heard how concepts drift and get lost in translation between specialists and executives; biodiversity and nature compete with other priorities for attention. Many firms rely heavily on external consultants - which can deliver momentum - but over-outsourcing slows internal capability building. Redirecting part of that spend to develop internal subject-matter expertise pays off in faster learning and durable execution.

So what?

Starting at the top, embed roles and responsibilities; equip functions such as procurement, site operations, product and risk teams with practical playbooks; build internal translation processes that converts specialist knowledge into commercial and operational choices.

5. Data and Method Complexity

Biodiversity and nature are inherently location-specific and multidimensional. Companies can be slowed by uncertainty – sometimes drifting into *'perfection paralysis'* where action stalls until information is 'complete'.²⁷ To be clear: we don't suggest decisions be made on guesswork; seeking greater certainty is important. But waiting for 100% certainty is rarely practical. Unlike greenhouse gases, there is no universally accepted metric for a company's 'biodiversity footprint'. Instead, firms must work with portfolios of indicators (e.g., habitat condition, species richness, water quality) that vary by place and context, plus qualitative evidence.²⁸

So what?

Start with decision-relevant baselines and a minimal viable indicator set; combine quantitative indicators with high-quality qualitative case evidence; strengthen methods over time. Remember that the metrics are there to drive action, and easily accessible widely accepted resources are available to guide companies on their priority actions per sector.²⁹

6. Fear of Greenwashing Backlash ('Greenhushing')

Some companies taking positive steps hesitate to publicise them. This greenhushing stems from fear that talking about modest biodiversity and nature efforts will invite scrutiny or scepticism without evidence that it will lead to strategic change. Recent risk data show biodiversity-linked greenwashing flags have doubled (from ~3% to ~6% of companies, 2021–2025) and regulators are escalating enforcement (e.g., a €25m fine for greenwashing; the UK *Digital Markets, Competition and Consumers Act 2024* enabling fines up to 10% of annual turnover)—all of which heightens reputational risk.³⁰ In a politicised context, some firms 'hide' or 'exit' alliances, while strong leaders hold or raise ambition—yet going quiet can stifle shared learning and stakeholder trust.³¹ It also means that the opportunity to inspire others is lost.

So what?

A measured, evidence-first communications approach is preferable to silence. Greenwashing risks are significant when companies don't address their most material impacts and dependencies but focus on seemingly 'nice to have' projects that are not core. Even if companies don't have all the answers, they should acknowledge where their biggest impacts and dependencies are and explain why and how they are taking action to tackle these. Invest in partnerships (e.g. with NGOs, academic institutions or other coalitions) to increase confidence in actions being taken.

What Enables Success?

Five Key and Connected Enablers for Action

In brief:

- Strong external signals and simple route maps (e.g. ACT-D, LEAP) give companies a scaffold to organise their nature strategy.
- Leadership commitment, integrated systems (risk, capex, procurement, sites) and aligned culture/incentives turn nature from an add-on into core business.
- Partnerships and credible evidence help derisk decisions, spread costs and move from isolated pilots to sustained, scalable action.

Our research and industry engagement point to critical enablers that help companies overcome the barriers. Cultivating these can unlock faster and bolder action on biodiversity and nature:

1. Regulatory and Market Drivers

External signals are strengthening in some areas, and also creating turbulence in others. Forward-looking executives use emerging disclosure and target-setting frameworks (e.g., TNFD-aligned reporting and Science-Based Targets for Nature) as enablers, not burdens. Some firms are already moving: Holcim worked with SBTN and became an emerging leader of science-based nature targets in 2024, gaining a head-start on risk management and reputation,³² with many biodiversity and nature projects already underway across its UK sites.³³ At the same time, investor expectations in some sectors are rising—major asset managers and banks now ask about biodiversity and nature impacts, and some have begun voting on biodiversity resolutions at AGMs.³⁴ However, in some cases, investor expectations are decreasing due to pushback by certain actors nationally and internationally.

ACT-D – a simple route map

ACT-D is a set of high-level business actions—Assess, Commit, Transform, Disclose—co-developed by leading nature and conservation organisations.³⁵ Business for Nature's Nature Strategy Handbook applies ACT-D to walk executive committees and boards through the main tools and frameworks—use it as a practical entry point for your company's nature strategy.³⁶

2. Leadership Commitment and Vision

There is no substitute for genuine top-level commitment. When the board and C-suite treat biodiversity and nature as strategic, set clear ambition, and link outcomes to core value creation and risk management, action cascades. Strong internal champions can drive change from within. Executive sponsorship legitimises trade-offs, unlocks budget, and signals expectations to business units. Public commitments (e.g., 'nature-positive by 2030' with place-based milestones) empower teams to innovate and align external partners.

Case in point

GSK, a multinational pharmaceutical company headquartered in the UK, has committed to being 'nature-positive by 2030' across its full value chain, from raw materials to the patient. As part of this ambition, GSK also set targets for 100% of its materials to be sustainably sourced and deforestation-free by 2030. The strategy has been publicly communicated and aligned with executive leadership, underlining its strategic importance at the highest level.³⁷

3. Integrated Strategy & Systems

Leaders weave biodiversity and nature into existing enterprise processes, so it becomes routine, not an add-on. That means embedding into risk management, capital allocation, procurement standards, product and packaging design, site operations, and audit/assurance.³⁸ Treat biodiversity and nature similarly to climate in enterprise risk: identify material dependencies/impacts, assign owners and set thresholds/controls.

Firms make progress when they create:

- clear operating procedures (e.g., supplier onboarding criteria; site management standards),
- enabling data infrastructure (baselines, location-specific indicators, auditable workflows), and
- performance management that pairs financial KPIs with biodiversity-and-nature KPIs.

4. Culture, Empowerment and Incentives

Capability scales when culture supports it. Equip and recognise employees who advance biodiversity-and-nature outcomes in their roles; create communities of practice and internal 'translators' who bridge specialist insight and commercial decision-making; spark these efforts by providing opportunities for employees to engage directly with the natural world. Don't downplay scale: we heard time and again how small, well-placed projects can unlock outsized learning and momentum when connected to a wider plan. Align incentives so longer-horizon resilience and avoided-risk benefits are visible in performance and investment decisions.

Enabler in action—Airbus UK

At Airbus in the UK, an employee engagement survey revealed strong demand for more outdoor and green spaces. That wellbeing 'hook' became the catalyst for a broader biodiversity programme across its main UK sites. The UK National Sustainability Officer team began with site-level biodiversity assessments, then introduced nature-friendly land management (such as 'No Mow May', reduced grass-cutting, wildflower planting in break areas), installed features like ponds and bug hotels using native species, and created a small urban Miyawaki micro-forest in a high-footfall area. At its largest aerodrome site, where aviation safety constraints are critical, Airbus is investigating perimeter hedgerows and wildflower mixes designed to attract only small, non-flocking bird species and collaborating with other airports to share viable solutions. Volunteer teams help deliver projects at low cost, and positive employee feedback has reinforced senior management support. Airbus is now using this experience as a pilot for an internal Framework on Biodiversity intended to guide other global sites in managing nature-related risks and opportunities. A key partner and collaborator in this work is The Wildlife Trusts, who not only support Airbus across their UK sites with the expertise needed to deliver effective nature regeneration projects, but also enable the business to contribute to social value-enhancing initiatives led by the charity.³⁹

5. Collaboration and Knowledge Partnerships for Credible Evidence

No company can tackle the biodiversity and nature challenge alone. Partnerships with NGOs, academic institutes and local authorities provide place-based expertise and legitimacy; industry coalitions accelerate pre-competitive standards and reduce transaction costs. We found that engaging external experts gave companies confidence to act despite uncertainties. Collaborating also spreads cost and risk – for instance, several companies have joined industry coalitions (e.g. the Fashion Pact in apparel, or cross-industry working groups under Business for Nature⁴⁰). The most effective collaborations are scoped to deliver decision-useful evidence: start with high-quality qualitative case studies and site narratives, then build to quantitative indicators and (where helpful) monetary valuation, tightening methods over time.

Bottom Line:

The most successful companies align leadership commitment, integrated systems and processes, and credible evidence, all reinforced by external market and policy signals. When these enablers click, businesses move from sporadic initiatives to sustained, scalable action on biodiversity and nature.

Six Types of Companies – Where Do You Stand?

In brief:

- Leadership teams should know where they're starting from, so we offer six company types as a simple rule of thumb for reflecting on current position and challenges.
- They range from Agenda Setters and Trailblazers to Emerging Leaders, Pressured Beginners, Backsliders and The Unengaged, each needing different kinds of support and intervention.
- Different parts of the same company may sit in different places on this spectrum; making those differences visible is a powerful basis for credible strategy and avoiding greenwash.

Not all companies are in the same place on their biodiversity and nature journey. It is useful for leadership teams to understand where they are starting from, so this guide uses two dimensions – internal readiness and external context – to sketch six broad types of company.

This is not about labelling firms, but about offering a simple rule of thumb to prompt honest reflection and discussion: the same organisation may show features of more than one type at once, with one business unit or function operating more like a Trailblazer while another is closer to a Pressured Beginner. The aim is to make this variation visible and actionable, rather than assume a single, uniform starting point.

1. Agenda Setters

These organisations shape the rules of the game. They have strong internal enablers (committed leadership, integrated strategy, in-house champions) and, crucially, they engage outward with change agents—NGOs, policy developers, standard-setters and peer coalitions—to define what 'good' looks like.

Agenda Setters convene, pilot frameworks (e.g., TNFD/SBTN), develop methodologies, and advocate for smarter policy and procurement signals. They influence industry standards and investor expectations, often becoming role models or partners for others. If your company has the will (leadership ambition) and is creating the way (shaping norms and incentives beyond your walls), you're acting as an Agenda Setter.

2. Trailblazers

These organisations deliver end-to-end execution at scale. They pair strong internal enablers with a supportive external context (favourable regulation, investor backing, customer pull) and move beyond compliance to embed biodiversity and nature across the business: resource allocation, supplier standards, product and site decisions, and assurance.

Trailblazers set ambitious targets (e.g., science-based nature targets), invest in place-based restoration, and report credible, decision-useful evidence.

3. Emerging Leaders

These companies have high internal commitment but operate in less mature external contexts. The CEO and team 'get it' internally, and they take action ahead of regulations, piloting tools and projects despite uncertain short-term return on investment. They move early, but within established frameworks, using voluntary standards, playbooks and norms that Agenda Setters helped shape and Trailblazers have operationalised—so efforts focus on piloting in priority hotspots and codifying what works, then scaling as policy, investor and customer signals strengthen. However, without external validation or resources, they can hit limits.

Emerging Leaders might wonder: how do we go from doing the right thing quietly to shaping the broader agenda? (e.g. 'What would it take for an Emerging Leaders to become an Agenda Setter?'). For these firms, connecting with like-minded peers and advocating for stronger external support can help amplify their impact.

4. Pressured Beginners

These companies have relatively low internal readiness but face mounting external pressure. The immediate catalyst is often a supply-chain questionnaire from a key customer demanding evidence on biodiversity and nature. Without leadership buy-in or internal expertise, responses skew reactive and compliance-oriented: boxes get ticked and basic disclosures are filed, but there's no real strategy to improve. The risk is doing the minimum, missing the chance to turn external pressure into advantage.

First steps: secure executive sponsorship; assess dependencies and impacts; set a simple policy with one or two high-leverage operational changes (e.g., supplier onboarding criteria, site standards); and build a baseline of credible evidence so future questionnaires become an opportunity to differentiate, not a fire drill.

5. Backsliders

Some organisations have already made commitments on biodiversity and nature but are now scaling back, delaying them, or going quiet. This is often driven by shifting political, legal, or market pressures, and tends to show up as exit (leaving alliances, retiring targets) or hide (rebranding commitments, reducing disclosure while keeping some work internal). The risk is a credibility gap: internal capability and momentum erode, and the firm becomes exposed to sudden tests, such as customer questionnaires, investor scrutiny, ratings or campaigns, that it is no longer ready to meet.

For executives in these companies: be honest about what is changing and why; ringfence a few non-negotiables (e.g., supplier standards, high-risk site actions); and keep governance and evidence-building in place so you can accelerate again when signals strengthen.⁴¹

6. The Unengaged

Finally, some organisations have yet to meaningfully engage with biodiversity and nature – they experience neither strong internal drive nor notable external pull. The Unengaged might simply be unaware, or view biodiversity and nature as irrelevant to their business. Often, they operate in sectors or regions where biodiversity and nature impacts are indirect, due to long / complex supply chains where risks are remote from the end product or service, or the regulatory environment is weak. However, no company is truly isolated from nature loss – their supply chains or future markets likely will feel the effects.

The Unengaged are vulnerable to sudden shocks (like a supply crisis, a reputational scandal or something as simple as a supplier questionnaire from a key customer) that could catch them unprepared. For executives in these companies, the guide is simple: start educating your team now on why biodiversity and nature matters to avoid nasty surprises, and seek quick wins (like assessing dependencies or risks) to move out of this high-risk zone.

Tip:

Have an honest conversation in your leadership team about where you stand today. Use the above categories as a rough lens. If you find your organisation is mostly reactive or unengaged on biodiversity and nature, acknowledge it – that's the first step to changing course. Many companies started there; what matters is the commitment to improve.

Understanding where your company fits across these types can inform your strategy. It helps diagnose your starting point in terms of internal capacity, external support and, crucially, any critical misalignment between different parts of the business.

Each type benefits from a different approach: an Engaged Leader might need more external partnerships and policy engagement, whereas a Pressured

Beginner may need to focus on building internal knowledge and leadership buy-in with the help of external expert support.

Some companies will also recognise a hybrid picture – for example, sustainability teams speaking boldly on nature while public affairs or lobbying functions push to maintain business-as-usual. Naming these tensions is important to avoid greenwashing and to support those trying to drive change from within.

There is no one-size-fits-all solution. A key takeaway from our work is that different types of companies – and different parts of the same company – require tailored interventions, not just more information thrown at them. The goal is progress: even if you start from The Unengaged or reactive position, over time you can build the enablers needed to move towards agenda-setting leadership.

From Insight to Action

Recommendations for the C-suite

In brief:

- Use a four-tier model—externalities, company response, operationalisation and evidence—to join up strategy, day-to-day decisions and learning.
- Focus the first two years on mapping dependencies and impacts, setting clear ownership and ambition, hard-wiring nature into core processes, and building a pragmatic journey based on evidence and measurement.
- Apply familiar management tools such as process and performance indicators so biodiversity and nature are managed with the same discipline as core functions like finance, risk and operations.

The four tiers—at a glance. To mature on biodiversity and nature, align leadership intent with day-to-day execution and credible evidence. The four-tier model is a simple scaffold that keeps everything connected:

1	<p>Externalities: Understand where your business depends on and affects biodiversity and nature across places and value chains, assess risks and opportunities</p>
2	<p>Company response: Policy and strategy from the board and C-suite</p>
3	<p>Operationalisation: Build the operating system (roles, processes, data, partnerships) that embeds biodiversity and nature into procurement, product, sites and risk</p>
4	<p>Evidence: Generate qualitative (case narratives) and quantitative (KPIs) evidence to learn, assure and signal progress—feeding back into strategy and develop over time with underpinning through assurance.</p>

1. Externalities → Map what matters and prioritise action

Develop a concise, decision-useful map of dependencies and impacts across your value chain and geographies. Pair risk and opportunity to avoid a compliance-only mindset; identify a small set of high-leverage hotspots (e.g., a commodity, a site, a product

line) where action shifts outcomes fastest. Use a materiality approach—preferably a double-materiality screen that looks at financial materiality (where biodiversity and nature affect enterprise value) and impact materiality (where your activities materially affect ecosystems and communities)—to focus scope and sequence.⁴² TNFD’s LEAP is one framework you could use to structure this process.

LEAP: A Four-Phase Approach⁴³

Locate: Map where your business interacts with nature (value chain, geographies, ecosystems)

Evaluate: Assess your dependencies on nature and your impacts on ecosystems and communities

Assess: Identify nature-related risks and opportunities for your business (financial, operational, strategic)

Prepare: Define responses, embed them into strategy/governance, and align with disclosure expectations.

2. Response → Be courageous, set direction, ownership and ambition

Signal that biodiversity and nature are strategic. Set an ambition (e.g., contribute to ‘nature-positive by 2030’ with place-based milestones) and assign clear executive responsibility (board committee + named C-suite owner). Define scope (sites, products, supply tiers), decision rights and risk appetite; align with global frames (e.g., Global Biodiversity Framework targets) for credibility. Direction beats perfection—set a north star now and refine as evidence improves. Get inspiration from existing strategies from other companies.⁴⁴

3. Operationalisation → Build the operating system to deliver

Translate strategy into an operating model. Consider using a coherent management framework such as the Star Model.⁴⁵

Star Model

- **Strategy:** ambition, scope, trade-offs.
- **Structure:** clear ownership in functions/ BUs; a small enabling centre.
- **Processes:** procurement and site standards, stage-gates in product/R&D, issue escalation.
- **Rewards:** targets and incentives that recognise longer-horizon resilience/ avoided risk.
- **People:** internal Subject Matter Experts (SMEs) and ‘translators’ who convert specialist insight into commercial choices (reduce over-reliance on consultants).

4. Evidence → Establish a pragmatic and realistic evidence journey

Start with high-quality qualitative evidence (site/supplier case studies, place narratives) and progress to quantitative indicators (habitat condition, species, water, etc.), and where decision-useful, monetary valuation. Focus on decision-relevance and assurance over exhaustiveness. Reporting should increasingly be integrated (finance + sustainability) with clear methods, baselines, limits and learning loops back to strategy and capital allocation.

Scorecard: What is Measured gets Managed

Use the same management logic you use in core functions such as finance, operations and procurement:

Any new initiative needs both process and performance indicators that link to enterprise value. The key message is that you don't need to reinvent management; apply your existing disciplines to biodiversity and nature.

Process indicators (are we doing the things?) e.g., % priority suppliers signed to nature policy; % new projects passing nature criteria at investment gate; % sites with habitat management plans.

Performance indicators (are those things working?) e.g., change in habitat condition at priority sites; % sourcing volume from verified better-practice sources; number of place-based projects delivering verified outcomes.

Keep it limited and decision-relevant: 3–5 indicators with clear owners, adequate resource and an internal assurance plan. Integrate these into the executive dashboard alongside strategic financial KPIs.

Leverage partnerships and external drivers to scale: Use coalitions and place-based partnerships (NGOs, academia, local authorities, regulators, suppliers, communities) to reduce cost/risk and build legitimacy. Engage proactively with TNFD/SBTN pilots where available and sector or value chain initiatives to help shape workable standards. Treat policy and finance trends (due-diligence rules, procurement standards, investor voting, sustainability-linked finance) as a planning assumption and position early.

Timeline for Action

Get clear	Pilot and learn	Scale and integrate	Extend and disclose
<p>Use a LEAP- or double-materiality style scan to map your key biodiversity and nature-related dependencies, impacts, risks and opportunities across the value chain and geographies.</p> <p>Identify 2–3 high-leverage hotspots (e.g. a product line, key commodity or site) where action could shift outcomes fastest.</p> <p>Secure executive sponsorship: agree a clear ambition and named ownership at executive- and board-committee level.</p> <p>Clarify scope and decision rights so teams know what is in bounds for the first wave of action.</p>	<p>Design a small portfolio of pilots in those hotspots (for example, one site, one supplier cluster, one product or region), aligned with ACT-D.</p> <p>Partner with NGOs, experts or local authorities to set credible baselines and practical interventions.</p> <p>Track a handful of simple indicators (e.g. supplier performance, water quality, employee engagement) alongside cost and operational impacts.</p> <p>Capture lessons and stories from these pilots to build the internal case and refine your approach.</p>	<p>Translate what worked into policies, standards and processes: procurement criteria, site management guidelines, product and packaging checkpoints, risk registers and resource stage-gates.</p> <p>Begin to embed biodiversity and nature into enterprise risk management and performance management, pairing financial KPIs with a small number of biodiversity- and nature-related KPIs.</p> <p>Align climate, circularity and nature initiatives so they reinforce rather than compete for attention and budget.</p> <p>Expand successful approaches to more sites, suppliers or business units, while retiring what has not delivered.</p>	<p>Broaden coverage, focusing on what is most material for your business model.</p> <p>Join or deepen participation in industry coalitions and place-based partnerships to reduce costs, share evidence and help shape workable standards and policy signals.</p> <p>Prepare, and where appropriate pilot, TNFD-aligned reporting and nature-related indicators for executive dashboards and external disclosure.</p> <p>Communicate transparently with employees, investors and other stakeholders about progress, gaps and next steps.</p>
0-6 months	6-12 months	12-18 months	18-24 months

Bottom Line:

Progress comes from coherence across tiers and silos—a clear response owned at the top, grounded in material externalities, enabled by an operating system and evidenced with credible verification. Use this as a one-page checklist in your next executive meeting, and review quarterly to keep momentum.

A Final Word: Seizing the Nature-Positive Opportunity

If you are a member of the C-suite, the time to elevate biodiversity and nature in your business agenda is now.

Use this Guide as a starting point. Challenge your teams with questions like:

- How do our operations depend on ecosystem services?
- What hidden risks or opportunities does biodiversity present?
- Where do we want to be in five years on this issue?

By asking these questions – and vitally, supporting your people to answer them – you set in motion a positive tipping point. In a few years, protecting and enhancing biodiversity and nature could be as normalised in business as digital transformation or financial auditing. Those who lead today will be the winners of tomorrow's economy that thrives in harmony with the natural world.

It's often said in management: 'What gets measured gets managed, and what gets prioritised gets done.' It's time to measure, prioritise, and manage biodiversity and nature as part of the core business.

The companies that do so will not only help avert environmental and social crises – they will future-proof their own success in a world that is demanding sustainability at pace and scale. The C-suite must seize this opportunity to steward their companies and our planet toward a more regenerative, resilient and prosperous future.

Embedding biodiversity and nature into business may sound challenging, but it is fast becoming the leadership imperative of our time. Companies that act decisively will find that protecting biodiversity and nature is not just a compliance exercise or a cost⁴⁶ – it can drive innovation (new products, markets, and services), strengthen supply chain resilience, and enhance brand value and trust.

The road to a nature-positive future will involve learning and adaptation. There will be uncertainties and course-corrections – and that's OK. What's important is to get started and stay committed. Each company's journey will be different, but by sharing knowledge and pushing together, we can reach the scale of change needed.

The C-suite has a critical role to play: by setting the tone at the top, allocating resources, and championing this cause, executives can turn biodiversity and nature from an important but ambiguous topic into a source of competitive advantage and pride.

Appendix

Glossary for Executives

ACT-D: High-level business actions—Assess, Commit, Transform, Disclose—co-developed by leading nature and conservation organisations. See section ‘What enables success?’

Biodiversity: The variability among living organisms from all sources including, inter alia, terrestrial, marine and other aquatic ecosystems and the ecological complexes of which they are part; this includes diversity within species, between species and of ecosystems.⁴⁷

Ecosystem Services: The contributions that ecosystems make to human well-being.⁴⁸

GBF: The UN’s Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (post-2022) setting global goals/targets to 2030/2050. This is a product of the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD)⁴⁹

LEAP: An integrated approach developed by TNFD to support organisations identify and assess nature-related issues. See section ‘From insight to Action’.

Nature: The natural world including all natural capital, processes, living organisms (including people) and phenomena like freshwater, air, oceans, forests, and soil. Nature provides vital ecosystem services such as water filtration and pollination.⁵⁰

Nature-based Solutions: Actions to protect, sustainably use, manage and restore natural or modified ecosystems, which address societal challenges, effectively and adaptively, providing human well-being and biodiversity benefits.⁵¹

Nature-positive: Societal goal to halt and reverse nature loss by 2030 on a 2020 baseline, and achieve full recovery by 2050.⁵²

TNFD: Taskforce on Nature-related Financial Disclosures—framework to assess, manage, and disclose nature-related impacts, risks, dependencies and opportunities.⁵³

SBTN: Science Based Targets Network—guidance to set science-based targets for nature.⁵⁴

About the RENEW Project

The **RENEW project** is a major interdisciplinary research initiative funded by NERC through the ‘Changing the Environment’ programme. Running from January 2022 to January 2027, it is co-led by the **University of Exeter** and the **National Trust**.

With over £12.5 million in core funding—plus partner match contributions and additional support from NERC and Natural England—RENEW represents a significant investment in addressing one of the most urgent environmental challenges of our time: the renewal of biodiversity.

Key features of the programme include:

- A **strategic alliance** between the National Trust and the University of Exeter
- An **interdisciplinary team** of over 60 researchers and support staff
- **33 partners** spanning the public sector, business and finance, and civil society

RENEW is designed to develop real-world solutions that respond to the complex drivers of biodiversity loss, and to support more regenerative relationships between people and nature.

This Guide is a deliverable of **RENEW Theme 4: Business and Finance**.

While considerable progress has been made in mainstreaming climate and carbon considerations into business decision-making, biodiversity remains a more complex and underdeveloped frontier. The aim of Theme 4 is to close this gap.

Theme 4 is working across four key fronts:

- **4.1 Championing Leadership**
Identifying and supporting biodiversity champions within the business and finance sectors—particularly those whose personal commitment, professional influence, or community ties position them to catalyse change.
- **4.2 Assessing Tools and Awareness**
Reviewing how existing biodiversity-related tools are being used in practice, with a focus on ‘double materiality’—i.e., how businesses impact and depend on biodiversity—and the extent to which this is shaping decisions.
- **4.3 Co-creating a Digital Biodiversity Toolbox**
Developing a user-centred platform to help decision-makers with resources, data visualisations, case studies and more.
- **4.4 Identifying Positive Tipping Points**
Exploring the levers that could trigger rapid shifts toward biodiversity renewal, and analysing the barriers that currently prevent these shifts.

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